

InterAcción y Perspectiv

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X
D.L. pp 201002Z43506

Enero-Junio 2022
Vol. 12 No. 1

Universidad del Zulia
Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Interacción entre autoridades públicas e instituciones de la sociedad civil en el ámbito de la prevención y combate a la corrupción
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6555412

Liudmyla Antonova *, Dmytro Mishchenko **, Ivan Bandura ***,
Vahif Abdullayev ****, Oleksandr Dolhyi *****

Resumen

El artículo corrobora la relevancia del estudio para la Ucrania moderna de la interacción de las autoridades públicas y las instituciones de la sociedad civil en el campo de la prevención y lucha contra la corrupción. Se realiza el análisis de las últimas investigaciones temáticas y publicaciones. El documento resume y destaca las principales direcciones y formas de mejorar la interacción de las autoridades públicas y las instituciones de la sociedad civil en el campo de la prevención y el combate a la corrupción e identifica las más efectivas y prometedoras. Se identifican las principales razones de la interacción destructiva entre las autoridades públicas y las instituciones de la sociedad civil (bajo nivel de conciencia legal, falta de mecanismos efectivos de retroalimentación entre la sociedad y el estado). Se dan instrucciones temáticas sobre una mayor interacción anticorrupción del estado (autoridades públicas) con la sociedad civil (instituciones de la sociedad civil). Se presenta un modelo conceptual del mecanismo de interacción entre el Estado y la sociedad civil en el campo de la prevención y combate a la corrupción. El artículo formula y resuelve un problema científico de actualidad en el campo de la administración pública, que consiste en resumir y destacar las principales direcciones y formas de mejorar la interacción de las autoridades públicas y las instituciones de la sociedad civil en la prevención y lucha contra la corrupción e identificar las más eficaces y prometedoras.

Palabras clave: Actividades anticorrupción, Administración pública, Instituciones de la sociedad civil, Corrupción, Autoridades públicas

Abstract

Interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption

The article substantiates the relevance of the study for modern Ukraine of the interaction of public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption. The analysis of the last thematic researches and publications is carried out. The paper summarizes and highlights the main directions and forms of improving the

interaction of public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption and identifies the most effective and promising of them. The main reasons for the destructive interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions are identified (low level of legal awareness, lack of effective feedback mechanisms between society and the state). Topical directions on further anti-corruption interaction of the state (public authorities) with civil society (civil society institutions) are given. A conceptual model of the mechanism of interaction between the state and civil society in the field of preventing and combating corruption is presented. The article formulates and solves a topical scientific problem in the field of public administration, which is to summarize and highlight the main directions and forms of improving the interaction of public authorities and civil society institutions in preventing and combating corruption and identify the most effective and promising.

Key words: Anticorruption activities, public administration, Civil society institutions, Corruption, Public authorities.

Recibido: 25/02/2022 Aceptado: 15/03/2022

* Doctor of Sciences in Public Administration, Department of Accounting and Audit, Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University, Mykolaiv, Ukraine. E-mail: antonovalv77@gmail.com

** Doctor of Sciences in Public Administration, Department of State, Local and Corporate Finance, University of Customs and Finance, Dnipro, Ukraine. E-mail: miscenk020@rambler.ru

*** Candidate of Sciences in Public Administration, Interregional Academy of Personnel Management, Kyiv, Ukraine. E-mail: bandurais@ukr.net

**** Black Sea National University named after P. Mohyla, Mykolaiv, Ukraine. E-mail: Vahifphd@gmail.com

***** Department for Development of Professional Development Programs and Needs Analysis of the Training Center, Ukrainian School of Government, Irpin, Ukraine. E-mail: saw_fliprnr@i.ua

1.- Introduction

At the present stage of development of the Ukrainian state, corruption is one of the most important political, economic and social problems, since it entails a number of negative consequences: it withdraws a significant amount of funds necessary for the life of the country from the domestic economy; significantly reduces the level of trust and worsens the state of the attitude of the population to the government and its bodies; slows down, or completely levels out the growth of the quality of life of the population, etc.

The modern experience of mutual relations between public authorities and civil society institutions demonstrates that through national specifics, economic, political, social and other conditions that reflect culture, history, traditions, etc. countries, the above entities do not have a universal way of effective interaction. Therefore, there is an urgent need to consider and improve the effectiveness of the mechanisms of this interaction and propose measures to establish constructive relations between public authorities and civil society institutions in modern Ukraine.

2. Literature review

The problem of mutual relations between public authorities of various types and levels and civil society and its specific representatives has long been the object of active scientific research by foreign scientists of various categories of knowledge. The variability of models of interaction between public authorities and society was once proposed by such scientists as: Bahoo, Alon, & Paltrinieri (2020), Bolya & Gillandersb (2018), Gamgani & Tonnac (2020). Novella-Garcia & Cloquell-Lozano (2021), Wickberg (2020).

The vector of our scientific research correlates with the areas of research activities of such scientists as: Adilov (2016), Havkalova & Hruzd (2014), Gajdareva (2013), Dzhabiev (2012), Kolosova & Ivanjuk (2011), Kabanov (2012; 2019), Murtazaliev (2012), Rylov (2019), Tihomirov (2013).

Paying attention to the existing scientific achievements and the rapid dynamics of changes in modern society, it should be noted that the range of thematic issues under consideration is not exhaustive. This gives grounds for further scientific theoretical and practical research of the multi-component phenomenon of corruption, in particular: state policy in the field of preventing and combating corruption in the context of comparing domestic and foreign experience; features and specifics of interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption at the present stage of development of the Ukrainian state. In this regard, the indicated topics of this stage of the study seem to be relevant, and the development of thematic recommendations and the provision of relevant proposals are practically significant.

The purpose of the article is to summarize and highlight the main directions and forms of improving the interaction of public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption and identify the most effective and promising of them. At this stage of the study used an interdisciplinary approach based on the principle of systematic, integrated and logical approaches

3. Results

The effectiveness of activities to prevent and combat corruption directly depends on the active participation of not only state, but also public institutions. As a multi-component social phenomenon, corruption includes economic, legal, social, political and ethical elements: in modern Ukraine, corruption manifests itself in all spheres of social interaction (Yankovyi, Koval, Dudka & Bykhovchenko, 2021). Under the current conditions, it is the institutions of civil society that can turn out to be a force to ensure that the authorities meaningfully implement legitimate public interests when making state-administrative decisions.

The key to an effective and efficient fight against corruption is constructive interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions. In interaction in the field of preventing and combating corruption, we understand the direct or indirect mutual influence of various subjects of preventing and combating corruption, in particular public authorities and civil society institutions of anti-corruption and other orientation, on each other and the relevant social environment to achieve pre-set joint activities. The goals are to reduce the level of corruption in the system of social administration.

It is our deep conviction that it is impossible to develop a special, clearly defined criterion to determine the anti-corruption purpose of a particular civil society institution: all civil society institutions existing in Ukraine, directly or indirectly, to a certain extent, can be involved in preventing and combating corruption.

Given the practical plane of relations between public authorities and civil society institutions, it should be noted that there is considerable disunity between these entities.

It should be recognized that to a large extent the effectiveness of anti-corruption policy today depends on the degree of involvement of civil society institutions in the activities to identify and publicize the facts of corruption offenses. Improving the effectiveness of anti-corruption policy at the present stage is mainly due to the strengthening of the role of civil society institutions in this area. This circumstance is due to the fact that the authorities, in principle, are not interested in actually fighting corruption. Without public participation and ensuring transparency in this process, as domestic practice shows, the government does not want and cannot really oppose what is its product. But the real scale of the spread of corruption in Ukraine, especially in its individual regions, today is such that it becomes the main reason for the destruction of the institutions of democracy and power in Ukrainian society. In fact, the government itself becomes a hostage to corruption (Murtazaliev, 2012).

In this regard, a significant number of proposals initiated by civil society institutions for cooperation in the field of combating corruption are not supported by state authorities and local governments, in particular, because of the unwillingness to violate established corruption ties and technologies, or are supported only verbally and are replaced by invitations to participate in formal events not related to the adoption and development of specific measures. The current situation has given rise to deep contradictions in assessments of the very possibility of establishing a constructive dialogue and mutual distrust, based on the fact that public authorities are a priori considered by civil society institutions as a key element of the corruption mechanism, and authorities, in turn, are afraid of "erosion" of their powers. and additional external control by public institutions (Murtazaliev, 2012).

As part of the problem of interaction between state and public institutions in anti-corruption activities, two main groups of reasons that contribute to the manifestation of corruption should be distinguished - a low level of legal awareness and the lack of effective feedback mechanisms between society and the state. The low level of legal awareness of citizens and other participants in legal relations to a large extent contributes to the spread of corruption. Organizing and holding events to raise the level

of legal awareness is a joint activity of the state and civil society institutions. Among the main directions of the implementation of the anti-corruption strategy of Ukraine should be the expansion of the system of legal education of the population. Raising the level of legal awareness in society is also one of the activities of a number of public organizations, such as Transparency International Ukraine. The interaction of the state with civil society in this direction is carried out by involving civil society institutions in the implementation of anti-corruption educational programs, organizing expert discussions, facilitating the provision of airtime in information and communication networks, etc. Another reason for corruption is the weak feedback of citizens with domestic public authorities, in particular, in the field of protecting their rights. The state, on the one hand, creates specialized bodies and positions to ensure such interaction (for example, the Commissioner of the Verkhovna Rada for Human Rights), and civil society institutions, on the other hand, help to strengthen this connection, representing the interests of their members (Kolossova & Ivanjuk, 2011).

Another problem in preventing and combating corruption is its high level of latency. Finding corruption is quite difficult. To effectively combat corruption, attention should be paid to its prevention to a large extent (Gajdareva, 2013).

The interaction of the state with civil society in order to reduce the level of corruption should be aimed in two directions:

- 1) overcoming the corruption consciousness and behavior of citizens, officials, and other participants in legal relations;
- 2) the fight against corruption manifestations in regulatory legal acts and the activities of public authorities.

Under the mechanism of interaction between the state and civil society in the field of preventing and combating corruption, we consider an artificially created system based on public authorities and civil society institutions with the help of a number of other elements of this system: functions, methods, tools, norms, principles, resources and measures carry out practical mutual influence on each other in order to achieve the goals of state policy in the field of preventing and combating corruption. This mechanism is multi-vector and polycomponent. The conceptual model of the mechanism of interaction between the state and civil society in the field of preventing and combating corruption is presented in Figure 1.

Given the lack of research information, special attention within the framework of this mechanism should be paid to the stages of anti-corruption activities. Interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption should permeate all stages of anti-corruption activities: from putting forward anti-corruption initiatives to monitoring the effectiveness of state policy in the field of preventing and combating corruption. At the stage of putting forward anti-corruption initiatives, the interaction of civil society institutions with public authorities should be carried out as follows: joint discussion of anti-corruption initiatives proposed by public authorities with interested civil society institutions; submission of proposals on public anti-corruption initiatives to public authorities and their joint discussion with interested

authorities; joint promotion of anti-corruption initiatives by civil society institutions and public authorities.

Figure 1. The mechanism of interaction between the state and civil society in the field of preventing and combating corruption

These forms of anti-corruption interaction between civil society institutions and public authorities are implemented during joint meetings, round tables, conferences and other organizational events. The criterion for the effectiveness of such interaction should not be the number of joint meetings on the problem of combating corruption, but the quantity and quality of implemented anti-corruption initiatives. Anti-corruption interaction between civil society institutions and public authorities arises from the joint participation of these subjects of anti-corruption policy on mutually beneficial terms and goes beyond the discussion of anti-corruption initiatives and is implemented as a joint activity (Kabanov, 2012).

The mechanism of interaction between the state and civil society in the field of preventing and combating corruption is characterized by specific qualitative and quantitative indicators, which include, for example: the number of measures to increase the level of legal awareness; the number of participants in legal relations involved in activities to increase the level of legal awareness; the number of public initiatives put forward aimed at preventing and combating corruption; the number of public anti-corruption examinations of draft regulatory legal acts; people's trust in power; the conviction of the population in the need to fight corruption; awareness of the population about the progress and results of the fight against corruption; the degree of involvement of civil society institutions in the implementation of anti-corruption measures together with state bodies; transparency of activities of public authorities, etc.

The implementation of the mechanism of interaction between the state and civil society in the field of preventing and combating corruption in social practice will contribute to the development of legal awareness of citizens, professional ethics, legal culture of officials of public authorities and local governments, improvement of rule-making and law enforcement activities.

The effectiveness of this interaction primarily depends on the effectiveness of the directions and forms of interaction and cooperation between public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption (in the implementation of a system of anti-corruption measures).

Considering corruption as a systemic phenomenon, it is important to counteract it in all directions, actively using the capabilities of all relevant actors, in particular, such as: the media, public organizations, trade unions and associations, social movements, public initiative bodies, political parties, the business community etc.

Table 1 reveals the content essence of the role and importance of civil society institutions in matters of interaction with public authorities in the field of preventing and combating corruption.

Table 1. The role and importance of civil society institutions in matters of interaction with public authorities in the field of preventing and combating corruption

Civil society institutions	Role and significance
<i>Mass media</i>	The media, in cooperation with public authorities, contribute to educating citizens in the spirit of respect for the law, contribute to the establishment of democratic values in the mass consciousness and understanding the danger of corruption. The mass media receive and disseminate information about the facts of corruption in all areas of public life, thereby exercising a kind of control over the activities of public authorities.
<i>Public organizations</i>	Public organizations (associations, associations, foundations, unions), in cooperation with public authorities, can develop and implement anti-corruption programs; ensure public control over bills; to carry out general activities aimed at developing recommendations on the fight against corruption; engage in anti-corruption propaganda; conduct special anti-corruption research (legal, sociological, economic, etc.).
<i>Professional unions and associations</i>	Professional unions and associations are called upon, in cooperation with the Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine, to monitor compliance with legislation in the field of employment, in particular in line with the fight against corruption, to represent and protect the social and labor rights of citizens from corruption; participate in the development of state employment programs.
<i>Social movements</i>	Social movements aimed at promoting intolerance of corruption, in particular through appropriate authorized actions, rallies, demonstrations, etc.
<i>Bodies of public initiative</i>	Bodies of public initiative together with public authorities are called upon to solve various social problems at the place of residence, study, work of citizens. At the same time, it is possible to carry out anti-corruption control over the implementation of acts of state authorities in solving local social problems.
<i>Political parties</i>	Political parties are called to form public anti-corruption opinion; to educate citizens in the spirit of intolerance to all forms of corruption; participate in the development of anti-corruption decisions of public authorities; participate in and monitor the conduct of elections and referendums; to develop and implement legal policy in legislation through its representatives.
<i>Business community</i>	The business community, as an integral part of civil society, takes part in activities to prevent and combat corruption, both by participating in discussions of draft regulatory legal acts and by presenting relevant initiatives.

Source: according to the source (Kolossova & Ivanjuk, 2011).

Taking into account the existing domestic regulatory and legal field and the scientific heritage on the interaction of public authorities with civil society institutions in the implementation of the state anti-corruption policy, we can single out three main areas in which it is most fully implemented: the first direction of interaction between civil society institutions and public authorities are manifested through the participation of representatives of civil society institutions in the work of specialized anti-corruption bodies - advisory, advisory, coordinating and expert permanent and temporary councils (commissions and working groups); the second direction of interaction is the interaction of civil society institutions with public authorities when using separate tools or mechanisms for combating corruption; the third direction of interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions is associated with the formation and development of the institution of public control over the implementation of the state anti-corruption policy (Kabanov, 2019).

The interaction of public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption must be ensured in the following main areas:

- improvement of the state anti-corruption policy, in particular in the field of anti-corruption legislation;
- ensuring, on a systematic basis, coordinated and purposeful joint actions of public authorities and civil society institutions;
- expanding the range of issues in the field of preventing and combating corruption, in the solution of which civil society institutions are involved;
- creation of a system of incentives for the active participation of civil society institutions in solving the tasks set by the state in the field of preventing and combating corruption;
- creating conditions for civil society institutions that promote accountability, openness and transparency of the activities of public authorities in making and implementing management decisions in the field of preventing and combating corruption;
- introduction of effective mechanisms for taking into account public opinion in the development of decisions by public authorities in the field of preventing and combating corruption and their improvement;
- formation of an anti-corruption worldview among the population;
- study and application of international experience of interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption (Murtazaliev, 2012).

The systemic and comprehensive process of preventing and combating corruption involves direct interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions, in particular, in the development of management decisions. Therefore, an important indicator of this interaction is the inclusion of representatives of civil society institutions

in the implementation of anti-corruption measures and in the composition of councils, commissions, etc., which are functioning in public authorities.

Taking into account the provisions of the current domestic legislation and law enforcement practice, it is possible to determine the following organizational and institutional forms of interaction between civil society institutions and public authorities:

- public councils under executive authorities;
- expert councils under public authorities;
- self-regulatory organizations;
- professional associations and public organizations;
- platforms for discussing issues of social and political life on the Internet, in particular, on the official websites of public authorities;
- publications in mass media;
- Institute of Public Expertise of Draft Regulatory Legal Acts;
- the institution of pretrial (out-of-court) appeal, etc. (Tihomirov, 2013).

However, in the modern realities of Ukraine, most of the above forms of interaction are not effective enough, which leads to the study of relevant foreign experience.

Modern European countries use three models of interaction between civil society institutions and public authorities, namely: 1) a normative model based on the liberal tradition; 2) a legitimization model based on a systematic approach, where civil society institutions perform important functions at the "entrance" of the political system; 3) an instrumental model, according to which the instrumental function of civil society institutions is to effectively solve social problems (Jargomskaja, Belokurova & Nozhenko, 2004).

Within the framework of these models of interaction, in order to minimize the negative impact of corruption on the very institutions of civil society, strict adherence to the implementation of the provisions of international legal acts is necessary. Civil society institutions should take into account the factor of corruption when developing strategies to improve the efficiency and productivity of their activities. The nature and scope of modern corruption is such that it even calls into question some of the key provisions of existing management theories (Bagmet, 2018; Korolchuk, Korolchuk, Myronets, Boltivets, Mostova & Koval, 2021). At the end of the XX century international civil society institutions promoted and disseminated interrelated phenomena: new public administration and anti-corruption policies. In this relationship, anti-corruption policy (in particular, the promotion of public ethics) is presented as a response to the failures and omissions of the new public administration (Bukanov, Kolesnyk, Tashkinova, Kotlubai, & Koval, 2019). Today, public administration and anti-corruption policy are prerequisites and consequences of each other (Sytnyk & Olesenko, 2020).

Modern public servants, even if they are not yet corrupt, by their direct or indirect actions significantly distort anti-corruption institutions by choosing the lowest probability

of detecting corruption when this probability concerns their own actions or inaction (Bolya & Gillandersb, 2018). As an example, in France, the reduction in the level of corruption among public servants was achieved through its public disclosure, indicating specific corrupt persons (especially of a political and financial nature) and the introduction and development of international principles of virtue and integrity, as well as strengthening the preventive approach to preventing corruption (Gamgani & Tonnac, 2020).

In addition, there is an opinion among European researchers that if the public authorities actively, systematically and for a long time promoted the foundations of moral conscious behavior among the population and there was a strong relationship between ethics and politics, the existing loopholes in the legislation would be less used. for corrupt practices. Therefore, the processes of promoting the provisions of public ethics deserve special attention (Novella-Garcia & Cloquell-Lozano, 2021).

Relevant for consideration is the experience of countries that are located at the crossroads of the European and Asian paths and have mutual positions with Ukraine. Given the common socialist past, the experience of Azerbaijan deserves special attention.

Paradoxically, the Azerbaijani society perceives corruption not as a social evil, but as an established phenomenon against the backdrop of reforms carried out in the country. This is confirmed by representatives of almost all categories of social and administrative relations, including politicians and statesmen, who by their real actions often create a corruption pyramid that undermines all initiatives to reform the social sphere and the economy of the republic. The bureaucracy, developing socio-economic programs, laws and by-laws, deliberately includes in them such articles and provisions that either contradict other by-laws, or create conditions for the free interpretation of certain articles. Therefore, an official can easily impose his principled and subjective position on this or that issue on other subjects of state-public relations (Dzhabiev, 2012).

Despite such a factual situation, the leadership of the Republic of Azerbaijan declares the fight against the phenomenon of corruption. National Azerbaijani leader Heydar Aliyev calls corruption a "common disease" and states that crime, bribery and corruption are the main issues that worry the public and cause its discontent (Adilov, 2016).

According to the current National Action Plan for the Development of Open Government in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the activities to apply the principles of transparency and openness of public authorities are built on a number of constructive provisions, among which the leading place is occupied by the provisions on cooperation of the latter with civil society institutions and ensuring public participation in socio-political the life of the country. This plan combines thematic events of different directions, including measures related to the fight against illegal actions that are incompatible with social norms and moral values. Appropriate measures are designed to help ensure the direct participation of citizens and public organizations in the fight against corruption, as well as to intensify the activities of public authorities in relation to the consideration of incoming applications in connection with the specified social problem

and corruption offense (improving the work on considering applications and complaints; developing cooperation with institutions civil society in the field of combating corruption;

The most common forms of interaction between public authorities of the Republic of Azerbaijan and civil society institutions are common and widely used, namely: promotion of anti-corruption initiatives; formal participation in the work of advisory bodies; holding general thematic events; information and explanatory activities in the field of preventing and combating corruption. However, the implementation of the forms of this interaction is actually not super-efficient.

In this regard, with the progressive development of public relations, the formation of an up-to-date, effective and viable institutional mechanism that provides comprehensive services in terms of stopping cases of corruption and increasing the transparency of building mutual relations between an official and a citizen on the basis of the legal provision of services to citizens can become super promising. the direction of ongoing reforms, envisaged for a long period. A good example is the creation of the State Agency for the provision of services to citizens and social innovations under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the formation of ASAN service centers as its structural component (Adilov, 2016).

Taking into account the variability of forms, means, models of interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions, we can argue that a priori there is no universal model of this interaction, which in absolutely all its aspects would be completely acceptable for modern Ukraine. But a certain experience in the directions and forms of interaction between the authorities and the public society of other countries, taking into account the historical traditions, mentality, legal framework and realities of modern Ukraine, can be partially and modified in our country.

The creation of an up-to-date and effective system of public authority today is an important factor in the gradual socio-economic development of Ukraine, which will ultimately ensure the formation of the Ukrainian state as a truly legal, social and highly developed European country with social stability and democratic governance. In the context of anti-corruption activities, the state should improve its policy in all areas of public life; support de facto, not de jure, institutions of civil society; develop, strengthen them and cooperate effectively with them. It is effective public administration that should ensure the constructive functioning of a practical organizational and legal mechanism for identifying, coordinating and implementing public needs and interests through the use of various legal means, the formation of subjective rights and obligations of participants in social processes and relations, the translation of their connections and mutual dependencies in certain legal relations (Havkalova & Hruzd, 2014).

The goal of achieving a truly democratic and effective mechanism for managing, protecting and protecting the rights of citizens, raising the level of legal awareness and the formation of law-abiding worldviews, we consider it necessary to put into practice a set of interconnected nationwide measures, among which the most significant are the following:

- organization of substantive and detailed legal propaganda in the media at all territorial levels;
- ensuring wide access of citizens to regulatory and legal information of all its types, except for information of secret significance (in accordance with the requirements of the current legislation of Ukraine);
- development and legislative consolidation of the latest forms and methods (with appropriate legal guarantees) of the real institutional involvement of citizens in the management, security and other activities of the Ukrainian state (Kolossova & Ivanjuk, 2011).

It should be noted that the effectiveness of the application of anti-corruption measures depends on a number of factors of a political, legal, managerial, economic and informational nature: compliance of the intensity of anti-corruption measures with the nature of corruption manifestations; correct placement of accents when choosing the most effective organizational and legal means of counteracting corruption manifestations, taking into account: assessment of corruption risks in a particular area or branch of public administration; the nature of the corruption offenses committed in this area and in a certain territory; data of sociological surveys, the state of corruption in a certain area of activity of public authorities; results of anti-corruption monitoring, in particular, law enforcement monitoring; other factors that allow to varying degrees to individualize the use of anti-corruption tools. The effectiveness of anti-corruption policy implementation depends on ensuring the necessary level of specialization of anti-corruption measures, taking into account the factors affecting corruption risks, on the correctly chosen object of anti-corruption impact: today these are persons holding positions in public authorities (Murtazaliev, 2012).

The key to increasing the level of effectiveness of anti-corruption activities in the country is the activity of civil society institutions and the support of public authorities for carefully prepared and thought-out public initiatives in the field of preventing and combating corruption. At the same time, it should be stated that in Ukraine and Azerbaijan the level of development of civil society is still at an insufficiently high level for the formation of an effective system of public control over the adoption and implementation of managerial decisions. With this in mind, the main emphasis should be placed on a comprehensive and all-pervasive process of raising the level of legal awareness and legal education of all participants in public legal relations.

4. Discussion

Counteraction and prevention of corruption is solved by different subjects using various means, tools and technologies, aimed at achieving a common result - reducing the level of corruption in the social management system. That is why the constructive interaction of various subjects of combating and preventing corruption in order to achieve their common ultimate goal is one of the conditions for the effectiveness of the state anti-corruption policy.

The interaction of public authorities with civil society institutions to prevent and combat corruption occurs in three main areas: involvement of representatives of civil society institutions in the activities of collegial anti-corruption bodies; providing them with conditions for the use of certain anti-corruption tools; exercising public control over the implementation of measures to prevent and combat corruption.

This requires the formation of a modern and effective mechanism for public prevention and combating corruption, which includes the following components: knowledge and active application of the existing legal framework by all citizens; overcoming corruption defects of legal consciousness; continuous and strict observance of anti-corruption prohibitions with the use of the control function; activation of anti-corruption activities within the framework of traditionally existing institutions and institutions created through public initiative; improvement of interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions in order to streamline the systemic-complex influence on corruption phenomena.

In our opinion, it is considered relevant to increase attention to the formation of a high sense of justice as the main preventive factor in preventing and combating corruption, as well as the use of sociological tools in law. Thus, there will be a decrease in the zone of misconduct and alienation from the law, and the scope of lawful behavior will expand.

Another component of effective prevention and combating corruption is the development of anti-corruption programs, which should become a component of the professional qualifications of all employees.

5. Conclusion

Activities to combat and prevent corruption by civil society institutions together with public authorities will be effective only when it becomes a collegial activity. Consistency and consolidation of anti-corruption efforts of different structures creates significant synergy. The effect of concerted actions far exceeds the result of disparate efforts in quantitative and qualitative terms of the composition of participants in various anti-corruption projects and programs. The conducted research convinces the relevance of further implementation of scientific developments in the field of preventing and combating corruption in various spectrums of consideration of this phenomenon. The study and solution of such issues as consciousness and human behavior, norm and deviation, the effectiveness of a set of measures to strengthen the rule of law, moral stimulation of exemplary behavior and activities, anticipation of corruption risks should help reduce the level of corruption in Ukraine.

We consider the following promising areas for further theoretical and practical research: development and implementation of relevant moral and moral means to reduce the scale of corruption in modern Ukraine; new directions of formation of anti-corruption consciousness of citizens and strengthening of their anti-corruption

motivation; anti-corruption education as an instrument of the state's anti-corruption policy

So, the article formulated and solved an urgent scientific problem in the field of public administration, which consists in summarizing and highlighting the main directions and forms of improving the interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions in the field of preventing and combating corruption and determining the most effective and promising of them. The results of this stage of scientific research, the above provisions and proposals serve as the basis for further theoretical and practical research of the national policy in the field of preventing and combating corruption in general and directions for improving the formation of modern mechanisms for preventing and combating corruption in particular.

Bibliographic references

- Adilov, N. (2016). Comparative analysis of the main aspects of the implementation of international law in the field of combating corruption in the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan. **Evrazijskaja advokatura**, 6 (25), 87-94. [in Russian].
- Bagmet, K. (2018). Regulation of Institutional Changes in the Social Sector of the National Economy: Conceptual Approach. **Economics Ecology Socium**, 2(4), 103-110. <https://doi.org/10.31520/2616-7107/2018.2.4-10>
- Bahoo, S., Alon, I. & Paltrinieri, A. (2020). Corruption in international business: A review and research agenda. **International Business Review**, 29 (4). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969593119309473>.
- Bolya, A. & Gillandersb, R. (2018). Anti-corruption policy making, discretionary power and institutional quality: An experimental analysis. **Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization**, 152, 314-327.
- Bukanov, H., Kolesnyk, A., Tashkinova, O., Kotlubai, V., & Koval, V. (2019). Social marketing in public administration of social service institutions. **Revista Genero & Direito**, 8 (6), 457-468.
- Dzhabiev, R. (2012). Shadow economy and corruption in Azerbaijan. **Mirovaja jekonomika i mezhdunarodnye otnoshenija**, 7, 84-91. [in Russian].
- Gajdareva, I. (2013). Anti-corruption in the civil service system as the main anti-corruption mechanism. **Jekonomika i socium**, 4 (9), 25-32. [in Russian].
- Gamgani, L. & Tonnac, A. (2020). Evolving measures to prevent and repress corruption in France. **Revue Francaise d'Administration Publique**, 175 (3), 677-691.
- Havkalova, N. & Hruzd, M. (2014). Interaction of public authorities and civil society institutions. **Aktualni problemy ekonomiky (demohrafiia**,

- ekonomika pratsi, sotsialna ekonomika i polityka**), 10 (160), 281-290. [in Ukrainian].
- Jargomskaja, N., Belokurova, E. & Nozhenko, M. (2004). **Why NGOs and authorities need each other. Models of interaction in the regions of the Northwest**. Public Policy: Soft Security Issues in the Baltic Region. SPb.: Norma, Moscow, Russia. [in Russian].
 - Kabanov, P. (2012). The main forms of interaction of civil society institutions with local government bodies in the field of combating corruption. **Aktualnye voprosy praktiki mestnogo samoupravlenija v Rossijskoj Federacii**, 1, 25-29. [in Russian].
 - Kabanov, P. (2019). **Social integration and development of ethnocultures in the Eurasian space**. Thematic area "Civil society against corruption" collection of materials of the All-Russian scientific and practical conference. Barnaul, Russia, 58-65. [in Russian].
 - Kolosova, N. & Ivanjuk, O. (2011). Civil society and the state in the fight against corruption. **Nauka i obrazovanie: hozjajstvo i jekonomika; predprinimatel'stvo; pravo i upravlenie**, 10 (16), 160-167. [in Russian].
 - Korolchuk, M., Korolchuk, V., Myronets, S., Boltivets, S., Mostova, I., & Koval, V. (2021). Competitive Properties of Trading Companies Managers. **Revista Geintec-Gestao Inovacao e Tecnologias**, 11(2), 941-954.
 - Murtazaliev, A. (2012). Theoretical and legal problems of interaction between authorities and civil society institutions in the field of combating corruption. **Vestnik Dagestanskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta**, 2. 5-9. [in Russian].
 - Novella-Garcia, C. & Cloquell-Lozano, A. (2021). The ethics of maxima and minima combined with social justice as a form of public corruption prevention. **Crime, Law and Social Change**, 75 (3), 281-295.
 - Rylov, D. (2019). Interaction of civil society and the state in the field of combating corruption. Social integration and development of ethnocultures in the Eurasian space. **Thematic area "Civil society against corruption" collection of materials of the All-Russian scientific and practical conference**. Barnaul, Russia, 334-337. [in Russian].
 - Sytnyk, H., & Olesenko, I. (2020). Solvency Control of the Enterprise in the Bankruptcy Prevention System. **Economics Ecology Socium**, 4(2), 14-23. <https://doi.org/10.31520/2616-7107/2020.4.2-2>
 - Tihomirov, Ju. (2013). **Participation of Civil Society Institutions in the Fight against Corruption: A Scientific and Practical Guide**. Institute of Legislation and Comparative Law under the Government of the Russian Federation, LLC "POLYGRAPH-PLUS", Moscow, Russia. [in Russian].

- Wickberg, S. (2020). New public management and the prevention of corruption: Rupture or continuity? **Revue Francaise d'Administration Publique**, 175(3), 661-676.
- Yankovyi, V., Koval, V., Dudka, T. & Bykhovchenko, V. (2021). Statistical assessment of project economic priority in company's investment management. **Revista Gestion de las Personas y Tecnologia**, 42, 98-119. <https://doi.org/10.35588/gpt.v15i42.5284>